

ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL SURVEY OF ANTI-ULCERATIVE COLITIS PLANTS IN THE SETU REGION, BEKASI, WEST JAVA, INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Ulcerative colitis is a chronic debilitating inflammatory disease that affects the colon and the rectum and typically involves the innermost lining or mucosal membrane. Due to unwanted effects of synthetic anti-colitis drugs, natural products are being explored as alternative or complementary therapy. This research aims to document and preserve the use of ethnomedicine to treat ulcerative colitis by people in the Setu Region, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia. Fieldwork was carried out from May to June 2025 using direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature. The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system. Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org). This research reports that 30 plant species are commonly used by people in the Setu Region to treat ulcerative colitis. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (53.3%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (16.7%), seed (10%), root (6.7%), fruit (6.7%), stem, and rind (respectively 3.3%). Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (80.0%) and infusion (20.0%). The results of this research confirm that people in the Setu Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of ulcerative colitis with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

KEYWORDS: Traditional medicine, Ethnomedicinal plants, Setu Region, Anti-ulcerative colitis.

INTRODUCTION

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic intestinal immune inflammatory disease, the course of which is protracted. As lifestyles continue to change, the worldwide prevalence of UC has increased annually.^[1] Currently, the treatment drug options for UC primarily include amino salicylic acid, glucocorticoids, and certain biological agents. In the course of these treatments, various adverse reactions can occur, including drug dependence, cytotoxicity, and liver and kidney damage.^[2] Additionally, relapse can easily occur after stopping the drug.^[3,4] Therefore, it is important to identify novel, safe, and more effective drugs for the prevention and treatment of UC. The majority of people living in developing countries depend on traditional medicine to treat various diseases.^[5] Medicinal plants are usually preferred for treating digestive disorders, such as diarrhea because they contain many elements that have the potential to increase effects and/or neutralize side

effects and are considered relatively safe in long-term use.^[6] Like other developing countries, people in Indonesia rely heavily on the therapeutic benefits of traditional medicine.^[7] One of the Region in Indonesia that still uses herbal plants as an alternative treatment, especially to treat UC, is Setu Region. This research aims to obtain detailed information about the use of herbal plants for alternative therapy for UC in Setu Region, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia using a field survey method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Setu is located in Bekasi Regency, West Java, Indonesia, with an area of 62.16 km². This area has an altitude of 40 meters above sea level with an average maximum air temperature of 33°C and a minimum of 25°C. Moreover, it is located between 06°14' 00" South Latitude and 107°00' 00" East Longitude. This area is a tropical

climate area that is mostly inhabited by Sundanese tribes (98%) and other tribes (2%). Vegetation in the study area is in humid conditions with an average rainfall of 351 mm/year.

Data Collection

An extensive field survey was carried out to obtain information about medicinal plants from the Sundanese tribe in the study area. To document existing information about medicinal plants from tribal practitioners, several field visits were conducted from May to June 2025 in the Setu Region, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia. During the research, ethnomedicinal information was collected from middle-aged and older tribal practitioners in their local language (Sundanese), through direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Information on local names of plants, plant parts used, preparation methods and administration routes (e.g., infusion, paste, juice and decoction) of all ethnomedicinal plants collected were recorded during the survey period.

Botanical Identification

Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature.^[8] The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to

the Cronquist classification system, except for Pteridophyta and Gymnospermae.^[9] Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org).

Ethics Statement

All participants provided verbal consent before the interview and gave consent to publish the information they provided.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that 30 plant species are commonly used by local people to treat ulcerative colitis (Table 1). This shows that the study location is affordable in terms of biodiversity. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (53.3%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (16.7%), seed (10%), root (6.7%), fruit (6.7%), stem, and rind (respectively 3.3%). The use of leaves is reported to be easier to prepare and easier to extract active substances from them for treatment. At the same time, leaves have less effect on the mother plant.^[10] Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (80.0%) and infusion (20.0%). These results are in line with previous research which reported that the forms of traditional medicine most widely used by the community were decoctions and infusions.^[8]

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal plants, local name, part used, mode of administration, and dosage uses in Setu, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia.

No	Species	Family	Local name	Parts used	Mode of administration	Dosage of use
1	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Alliaceae	Bawang Putih	Rhizome	Infusion	50 grams once a day
2	<i>Alpinia purpurata</i> K. Schum	Zingiberaceae	Lengkuas	Rhizome	Decoction	100 grams once a day
3	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> Nees	Acanthaceae	Sambiloto	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
4	<i>Annona muricata</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sirsak	Leaf	Infusion	150 grams once a day
5	<i>Anredera cordifolia</i> (Ten.) Steenis	Basellaceae	Binahong	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
6	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (L.) Kuntze	Theaceae	Teh Hijau	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day
7	<i>Canna discolor</i> L.	Cannaceae	Ganyong	Root	Decoction	100 grams once a day
8	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Caricaceae	Pepaya	Seed	Decoction	150 grams once a day
9	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J. Presl	Lauraceae	Kayu Manis	Stem	Decoction	50 grams once a day
10	<i>Coleus scutellarioides</i> (L.) Benth.	Lamiaceae	Miana	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day
11	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kunyit	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
12	<i>Eleutherine palmifolia</i> (L.) Merr	Iridaceae	Bawang Dayak	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day
13	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Clusiaceae	Manggis	Rind	Infusion	150 grams once a day
14	<i>Hibiscus tiliaceus</i> L.	Malvaceae	Waru	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
15	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Jarak	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day
16	<i>Kaempferia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kencur	Rhizome	Infusion	250 grams once a day
17	<i>Maranta arundinaceae</i> L.	Manantaceae	Tanaman Garut	Root	Decoction	150 grams once a day
18	<i>Melastoma candidum</i> D.	Melastomataceae	Senggani	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day

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19	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Pare	Leaf	Decoction	250 grams once a day
20	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Mengkudu	Fruit	Infusion	100 grams once a day
21	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	Moringaceae	Kelor	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
22	<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.	Myristicaceae	Pala	Seed	Decoction	50 grams once a day
23	<i>Nigella sativa</i> L.	Ranunculaceae	Jinten Hitam	Seed	Decoction	200 grams once a day
24	<i>Phaleria macrocarpa</i> (Scheff.) Boerl)	Thymelaceae	Mahkota Dewa	Fruit	Decoction	250 grams once a day
25	<i>Piper betle</i> L.	Piperaceae	Sirih	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
26	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Myrtaceae	Jambu Biji	Leaf	Decoction	150 grams once a day
27	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i> L.	Asteraceae	Tempuyung	Leaf	Decoction	200 grams once a day
28	<i>Syzygium polyanthum</i> (Wight) Walpers	Myrtaceae	Salam	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
29	<i>Tinospora crispa</i> L.	Menispermaceae	Baratawali	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Jahe	Rhizome	Decoction	100 grams once a day

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research confirm that people in the Setu Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of ulcerative colitis with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

REFERENCES

1. Kobayashi T, Siegmund B, Berre CL, Wei SC, Ferrante M, Shen B, et al. Ulcerative colitis. *Nat Rev Dis Primers.*, 2020; 6(1): 74.
2. Losa A, Gomes R, Mourão FR, Cardoso SS, Vieira PM, Correia MR, et al. Drug-related adverse reactions in pediatric inflammatory bowel disease. *J Clin Pharmacol.*, 2024; 64(1): 103-110.
3. Hindryckx P, Jairath V, D'Haens G. Acute severe ulcerative colitis: from pathophysiology to clinical management. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol*, 2016; 13(11): 654-664.
4. Tambuwala MM. Natural nuclear factor kappa beta inhibitors: Safe therapeutic options for inflammatory bowel disease. *Inflamm Bowel Dis.*, 2016; 22(3): 719-723.
5. Asrie AB, Abdelwuhab M, Shewamene Z, Gelayee DA, Adinew GM, Birru EM. Antidiarrheal activity of methanolic extract of the root bark of *Cordia africana*. *J Exp Pharmacol.*, 2016; 8: 53-59.
6. Gilani AH, Rahman AU. Trends in ethnopharmacology. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2005; 100(1-2): 43-49.
7. Alkandahri MY, Sujana D, Hasyim DM, Shafirany MZ, Sulastris L, Arfania M, et al. Antidiabetic activity of extract and fractions of *Castanopsis costata* leaves on alloxan-induced diabetic mice. *Pharmacogn J*, 2021; 13(6Suppl): 1589-93.
8. Bieski IGC, Santos FR, de Oliveira RM, Espinosa MM, Macedo M, Albuquerque UP, de Oliveira Martins DT. Ethnopharmacology of medicinal plants of the Pantanal Region (Mato Grosso, Brazil). *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.*, 2012; 2012: 1-36.
9. Cronquist A. The evolution classification of flowering plants. The New York Botanical Garden, New York, NY, USA, 2nd edition, 1988.
10. Ahmed S, Ahmad M, Swami BL, Ikram S. A review on plants extract mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles for antimicrobial applications: Agree expertise. *J Adv Res*, 2016; 7(1): 17-28.